

Synthesis, X-Ray Diffraction Studies and Electrical Properties of Iron(III), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) Chelate Polymers with 2,3,5,6-Tetrahydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone

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In continuation of our earlier work¹, we report here the synthesis of coordination polymers of Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with 2,3,5,6-tetrahydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone (THBQ). The compounds have been characterised by elemental analysis, ir and magnetic moment data. The order of decomposition reaction and activation energies have been evaluated by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Dielectric constant and d.c. conductivity have also been measured. From dielectric constant, a.c. conductivities have been calculated. On the basis of X-ray powder diffraction studies cell parameters are calculated, the patterns indexed and the crystal symmetry is determined.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds are dark coloured solids and are insoluble in water and in common organic solvents. They are stable at room temperature and non-hygroscopic. Elemental analyses of the compounds (Table 1) indicate that the metal to ligand ratio is 1 : 1.

The presence of coordinated water in the polymer is manifested by a broad weak ir band in the high frequency region² and it is further supported by the presence of a band³ around 700 cm⁻¹. The absence of the ligand band at 3290 cm⁻¹ (OH) in the ir spectra of the coordination polymers indicates the replacement of H by metal ion. A shift of $\nu_{C=O}$ band to lower frequency further supports the participation of phenolic OH in coordination. Shift of C=O frequency in the ligand by 50 cm⁻¹ to the lower frequency side indicates the involvement of C=O in chelation. Further, the far-infrared spectra of the complexes show bands at 350–500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to ν_{M-O} bands⁴. The tentative structure of the polymer is given in Fig. 1.

Magnetic moments of the Fe^{III}, Co^{II} and Ni^{II} coordination polymers are 5.87, 4.7 and 2.7 B.M. respectively which is lower than the expected values indicating their polymeric nature. This favours the high-spin octahedral geometry and their paramagnetic nature.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA AND ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS

Sl no	Compd	Analysis % Found / (Calcd)			Dielectric constant	loss (tan δ)	σ_{ac} $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	σ_{dc} $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$
		C	H	M				
1	THBQ	—	—	—	3.76	—	—	3.37×10^{-10}
2	Fe-THBQ	18.60 (18.57)	2.92 (3.09)	29.00 (28.80)	17.77	0.28	2.76×10^{-1}	5.66×10^{-11}
3	Co-THBQ	17.80 (18.29)	3.08 (3.07)	29.30 (29.90)	9.65	0.20	1.07×10^{-7}	6.30×10^{-11}
4	Ni-THBQ	18.40 (18.32)	3.06 (3.08)	26.00 (26.80)	6.99	0.19	7.38×10^{-8}	7.03×10^{-11}

Fig 1 Structure of coordination polymer THBQ (M = metal ion)

The electronic spectra of the Fe^{III} complex show a weak band around 23000 cm^{-1} , of Co^{II} complex show three bands around 13000 , 24000 and 26000 cm^{-1} and of Ni^{II} complex show two $d-d$ bands around 16000 and 26000 cm^{-1} and are assignable to octahedral geometry.

From D.S.C. plots (not shown) the order of the reactions and activation energy have been evaluated⁵. The activation energies for THBQ, Fe-THBQ, Co-THBQ and Ni-THBQ are found to be 9.37, 4.82, 27.40 and 12.88 kcal mol^{-1} respectively. This shows that the coordination polymers are more stable than the ligand except the Fe^{III} polymer and the order of thermal stability of the polymers is Co-THBQ > Ni-THBQ > Fe-THBQ.

Alternate single and double bonds are present in the polymers which provide a suitable channel for the flow of electrons and exhibit unusual electrical properties⁶. Keeping this in view d.c. and a.c. conductivity and relative dielectric constant values of the ligand and its polymers with Fe^{III} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} have been studied. Variation of dielectric constant with frequency for THBQ and the coordination polymers with Fe^{III} , Co^{II} and Ni^{II} have been studied. It is seen that the polymers have much higher

values of dielectric constant when compared to TBHQ. It is also observed that for the ligand, the dielectric constant is almost frequency-independent while for the coordination polymers dielectric constant is higher at lower frequencies. Dielectric loss ($\tan \delta$) for Fe-THBQ is higher at lower frequency. It is also observed that the loss for Fe-THBQ has peaks at 2 and 15 kHz. The loss for Ni-THBQ is larger at lower frequencies with only one peak at 15 kHz. Table 1 shows the values of dielectric constant and loss at 100 kHz for the ligand (THBQ), Fe-THBQ, Co-THBQ and Ni-THBQ.

The dielectric constant and the a.c. conductivity values are also shown in the table. The conductivity induced in the polymers is believed to be due to the nature of conjugation. The conductivity in such polymers is known to be electronic and not ionic⁶.

From the X-ray diffractograms, the patterns have been indexed by trial and error method, keeping in mind the characteristics of the various symmetry systems, till a good fit was obtained between the observed and calculated $\sin^2 \theta$ values. The unit cell parameters were calculated from the indexed data⁷.

The diffractograms of THBQ and Fe^{III} polymer with ligand consists of 16 reflections each between 10° and 68° (2θ) for ligand and 10° and 60° (2θ) for the polymer. $\sin^2 \theta$ values for all the observed reflections have been listed for ligand and for polymer. The observed values of the ligand and polymer fit well in a tetragonal system to give a unit with the lattice parameters (Table 2). The diffractograms of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} polymers with THBQ consist of 20 and 17 reflections respectively, between 10° and 60° (2θ) for the Co^{II} polymer and 10° and 48° (2θ) for the Ni^{II} polymer. $\sin^2 \theta$ values for all the observed reflections have been listed for the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} polymers. The observed values of the Co^{II} and Ni^{II} polymers with the ligand fit well in the orthorhombic system to give a unit cell with lattice parameters shown in Table 2.

In conclusion, we can state that the coordination polymers are thermally stable and because of the presence of alternate single and double bonds in the polymers, they are good conductors.

Experimental

2,3,5,6-Tetrahydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone (THBQ) (Aldrich), ferric chloride, nickel and cobalt acetates (all AnalaR) were used.

TABLE 2—LATTICE PARAMETERS

Compd.	<i>a</i> (Å)	<i>b</i> (Å)	<i>c</i> (Å)	Cell volume (Å) ³
Ligand	10.589	7.349	—	824.02
Fe ^{III} - polymer	9.280	6.460	—	556.30
Co ^{II} - polymer	7.834	7.290	6.12	349.50
Ni ^{II} - polymer	7.600	7.400	6.10	347.00

The metal chelate polymers were synthesised by mixing equimolar alcoholic solutions of the metal salts and the ligand. The mixture was refluxed for 3–4 h on a water-bath and the solids separated slowly were washed with hot water and ethanol.

The elemental analysis data of the metal chelate polymers were obtained from Regional Research Laboratory, Hyderabad. The ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 283 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was determined by using

a Gouy magnetic balance. D.S.C. was recorded on a Mettler T.A. 200 C instrument. Dielectric constant and loss ($\tan \delta$) were measured at room temperature using a G.R. 1620 A capacitance assembly in conjunction with a laboratory-built three-terminal cell. An external oscillator (Agronic 72) was used at high frequencies. The conductivity ($\sigma_{a.c.}$) was evaluated using the relation, $\sigma_{a.c.} = E \cdot E_0 \cdot \omega \tan \delta$, where E_0 is the vacuum dielectric constant and ω the angular frequency. The d.c. conductivity at room temperature was measured using a Kiethley 610 C electrometer. X-Ray powder diffractograms were obtained with the help of a Philips diffractometer at a chart speed of 2° (2 θ)/min using the scale 2° = 1 cm.

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